

D2.2 Business model of the digital solutions used for assisting elderly people with cognitive impairments

WP2 Y1Q2

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 643588

INDEX

1	Introduction	7
2	Objective and Work Plan.....	7
3	Literature Analysis and Projects	9
3.1	Methodology	9
3.2	Main Projects.....	11
3.2.1	Companion.....	12
3.2.2	Cogknow	12
3.2.3	Remember me.....	13
4	Business Models Analysis	14
4.1	Business Model Benchmark	14
4.1.1	Service Domain.....	15
4.1.1.1.	Italy.....	15
4.1.1.2.	Spain.....	16
4.1.1.3.	Sweden.....	17
4.1.1.4.	Israel	17
4.1.1.5.	Synthesis	17
4.1.2	Technology Domain.....	18
4.1.2.1	Italy.....	18
4.1.2.2	Spain.....	19
4.1.2.3	Sweden.....	20
4.1.2.4	Israel	21
4.1.2.5	Synthesis	22
4.1.3	Organization Domain	23
4.1.3.1	Italy.....	23
4.1.3.2	Spain.....	24
4.1.3.3	Sweden.....	25
4.1.3.4	Israel	25
4.1.3.5	Synthesis	26
4.1.4	Financial Domain	26
4.1.4.1	Italy.....	27
4.1.4.2	Spain.....	28
4.1.4.3	Sweden.....	28
4.1.4.4	Israel	29
4.1.4.5	Synthesis	29
4.1.5	Concluding Discussion.....	30
4.2	Business Model Synthesis	31
4.2.1	Customer Segments	32

4.2.2	Value Propositions	34
4.2.3	Channels	39
4.2.4	Customer Relationships	40
4.2.5	Revenue Streams	42
4.2.6	Key Resources	43
4.2.7	Key Activities	44
4.2.8	Key Partnerships.....	46
4.2.9	Cost Structure.....	48
5	Conclusions.....	50
6	Main References Considered	54
	Appendix	58

Project Number:	643588
Project Title:	DECI
Document Type:	Final Version of the Deliverable

Document Identifier:	
Document Title:	Business model of the digital solutions used for assisting elderly people with cognitive impairments
Source Activity:	WP2
Editor:	FPM
Authors:	Luca Gastaldi, Simona Solvi, Niccolò Ballerio, Andrea Pistorio, Sathish Kumar Sankar, Andreas Hellström, Monika Jurkeviciute, Patrik Alexandersson, Nicola Restifo, Roberto Moser, Wander Kenter
Status / Issue:	Version 13 / F
Date Last Change:	07/01/16 14:13
File:	DECI_D2.2_v13.docx
Contractual Delivery Date:	30 November 2015
Actual Delivery Date:	30 December 2015 (Version 13)

Document History:	
31 July 2015	Definition of ToC
2 November 2015	Draft shared with WP2 partners of DECI Consortium
9 November 2015	Draft shared with DECI Consortium
30 November 2015	Version implementing Consortium feedback
30 December 2015	Version to be shared with Project Officer

Executive Summary

This deliverable aims at identifying the variables to be considered in order to describe the Business Model (BM) of a digital solution used for assisting elderly people with Mild to Moderate Cognitive Impairments (MCI).

The objective is reached through an analysis of relevant literature, case studies, good practices and key trends related to digital service solutions explored through Co-Creation Workshops (CCWs) organised with patients, caregivers and physicians. The analysis allows to identify the most suitable papers/projects/experiences, focusing on the most relevant variables for providing social-care services through digital solutions to the specific segment of users tackled in DECI.

First, four interrelated domains – service, technology, organisation and finance – are considered in order to gain a holistic view of the key points characterizing the BM, with respect to the STOF framework (Bouwman et al., 2008). One CCW has been accomplished in each country in order to collect preliminary evidence to be deepened through literature and project analysis.

Literature analysis exploited the 9 building blocks described by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010) in the renowned “Business Model Canvas”, and is characterized by the adoption of two lenses: the first one considers the viewpoint of the end-user of the solution, while the second one takes into accounts all the actors that are in charge of realizing, managing and delivering the service or part of it.

Customers segments, value propositions, channels, customer relationships, revenue streams, key resources, key activities, key partnerships and cost structure are all linked variables that should be taken into account to create, delivers and capture value.

The starting point are customer segments, characterized by key actors not only related to patients (with dementia, Amnesic MCI or Non Amnesic MCI), but also to caregivers, healthcare specialists and organizations. Any decision to focus on one or some groups of customers will affect choices related to “intermediate” customers. Furthermore, the caregiver has a twofold role related not only to support the patient in technology usage, but also acting as a connection to the healthcare system. Thus, the caregiver is both a recipient of the value proposition and a channel through which it is delivered.

Value propositions are various and most of them seems to be characterized by being complementary to each other, both from the patient and the system perspective: for instance, providing a monitoring system without establishing a proper solution of data integration among actors that allows also the collaboration of the GP will result

as a poor solution. Furthermore, these aspects should be contextualized both within the various National Health Systems and with technologies coherent with needs.

Moreover, these technologies should be personalized – for example by mapping patient’s activities – in order to empower both patient and caregiver, while the specific Health Systems affects also the kind of relationships among all these actors.

In particular, according to customer segments addressed with specific value propositions, business relationships that generates revenue streams could involve three market segments: the end-user (B2C), another company (B2B) or a public administration (B2P). The latter could affect the effective adoption and use of every digital solution through actions such as incentives, awareness campaigns or norms. Anyway, all the blocks of the BMC are influenced by the context; therefore, also the interplay among key resources – useful to design, develop and sustain the BM – depends on contextual factors.

Evidences from literature and case studies are completed with feedback and recommendations gathered from all Consortium partners, thus profiting of a different range of perspectives: from a technical and managerial view to a clinical approach. The opportunities of sharing opinions and comments were both in presence (such as during the Co-Creation Workshops, project meetings and skype calls) and off line.

The *fil rouge* among the key evidences arisen from the analysis will constitute the starting point for further activities of DECI Project.

1 Introduction

This deliverable is the outcome of Task 2.2: “Business model of the digital solutions used for assisting elderly people with cognitive impairments”.

The document aims to define a first draft of a BM for a digital solution addressed to elderly people with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) by providing findings of the various elements characterizing the overall system that allow the provision of digital services/solutions. This goal is reached through a mix of elements both from literature analysis and practical insights derived from Co-Creation Workshops (CCWs). The synthesis will also represent the starting point to discuss the BM in WP3, merging considerations from WP1 and WP2 in order to realize a final BM suitable for DECI project.

2 Objective and Work Plan

This document provides a general description of the various elements of BMs characterizing digital services/solutions for assisting elderly people with MCI.

The goal is addressed through the activities depicted in Figure 2-1. First, a literature review was performed in order to shade lights on the main topics of the project. Then, the evidences collected have been synthetized using two different approaches:

- The STOF Framework (Bouwman, de Vos, & Haaker, 2008);
- The BM Canvas (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010).

Figure 1 represents the logic followed in structuring the deliverable as well as the connections with other WP/Tasks.

Figure 2-1 Organization of the document

The first analysis concerns the state of the art, good practices and trends related to digital services and solutions for the assistance of older people and the main variables useful to describe the relative BM. This analysis has been conducted through the study of academic and grey literature regarding various traits of the services for patients with MCI or characteristics of the patients themselves. This analysis also exploits the knowledge related to the target and needs of patients with MCI and the benchmarking of digital solutions gained from the WP1 and WP2.1 respectively.

The second analysis, pursued through the STOF framework, provides an overall picture of the BM from four perspectives: service, technology, organization and finance. These viewpoints are interrelated and enable detailed analyses of the critical design issues that shape, activate and sustain the BMs.

The last level of analysis takes the perspective of the BMC framework of and it includes the following elements: (i) customer/patient segments with specific needs to be satisfied; (ii) value proposition offered; (iii) channels through which it is possible delivering the value proposition;(iv) relationships with customer segments to be sustained (v) activities, resources and costs required to create, offer and sustain the value proposition; (vi) key partnerships to be maintained in order to make the digital solution sustainable; (vii) revenues streams required to ensure the sustainability of the digital solutions.

The remainder of the document is organised as follows:

- §3 is divided into two main paragraphs:
 - §3.1 concerns the methodology adopted to conduct the literature analysis.

- §3.2 provides a description of three projects in which digital service solutions are used to support patients with similar needs to those required for DECI.
- §4 is divided into two main paragraphs.
 - §4.1 deals with the categorization of the findings into the 4 dimensions of the STOF framework.
 - §4.2 groups the findings of the literature analysis and the evidences related to the STOF framework into the 9 building blocks of the BM Canvas framework.
- §5 concerns conclusions, thus it provides the *fil rouge* among the various findings.

3 Literature Analysis and Projects

The analysis of the literature focuses on papers and relevant projects describing the BMs for providing social-care services through digital media to elderly people with MCI.

3.1 Methodology

A literature review has been conducted to identify the most relevant articles dealing with the focus of this deliverable. The research process has been organized in 3 main steps, as showed in Figure 3-1. The search engines adopted to perform the research are Web of Science™ and Google Scholar™.

Figure 3-1 Search strategy

The **first step** is useful to deepen the knowledge related to the design of BM, with particular focus on BMC developed by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010). The search was also finalized to find out connections between BMs and healthcare services and settings.

The **second step** of search strategy was primarily based on the combination of different **keywords**, composing a list of queries to be imputed within the search engines. The keywords are referred to 3 areas: (i) Technology; (ii) Clinical domain; (iii) STOF/BM, and are listed below:

- **Technology:** ICT; Digital; IT; Information Technology;

- **Clinical domain:** Elderly; Cognitive impairment; Dementia; Alzheimer; Frail; Disable.
- **STOF/Business model:** Business model; Canvas; Osterwalder; STOF.

First, combinations of three keywords, one for each areas using Boolean connectors, were imputed for the research process, (e.g. ICT AND Cognitive Impairment AND Canvas; Digital AND Cognitive Impairment AND Canvas). At the end of these searches 1,149 articles were found, 819 selected after removing 330 duplicates.

Nevertheless, the strategy pointed out a variety of topics, mostly of them related to technical aspects and/or not related to healthcare context. For example, various papers/books belonged to publications in the field of automation, electronics and other specific scientific branches. As a result, the major part of the papers was not relevant with respect to our business perspective.

Only few papers/books were found strictly relevant to the goal of the project. Thus, a complementary search strategy was implemented in order to enrich the previous search with more specific and targeted papers. With this aim, **snowballing technique** was based on the previous selected articles using as drivers the same authors, journal or references. Furthermore, projects that have various similarities with DECI in terms of technology adopted or kinds of patients to whom the service is designed for, were used as input to extend the literature search.

At the end of these search, 29 papers and books were selected for their relevance and analyzed as core literature of this document. The research applied for full-text articles and abstract and, in this last case, those considered relevant were obtained. All the selected articles are those that effectively describe one or more key elements related to BM, or provide some relevant detail helpful to a better understanding of the dynamics, issues and potentialities concerning digital service solutions.

Researchers conducted the process of evaluation and selection of the papers during the periodic meeting of the research team. These meetings were useful to discuss, to share the findings and validate the relevance of the articles. Finally, each article was reported in a spreadsheet file containing the following information: (i) Title; (ii) Year of publication; (iii) Authors; (iv) 4 elements of the STOF framework; (v) 9 Building blocks of the BMC.

The list of all the papers and books considered and their specific contribution with respect to the 9 building blocks of the BMC and to other relevant issues addressed within this task of the project are outlined in the Appendix.

Another input for this WP is represented by the Outcome Reports of the four Co-Creation Workshops (CCWs) – held in Milan, Madrid, Goteborg and Tel Aviv – that represent the four pilot locations of the DECI project. Workshops, especially those held in Europe, were characterized by similar aims and objectives but, at the same time, the variety of countries chosen allowed to consider different elements that can be context-specific and to analyse the following aspects from various viewpoints:

- Stakeholder’s current roles and responsibilities regarding the care of MCI;
- Gaps and needs amongst target population in the current care model;
- Possible solutions through existing and available digital technologies;
- Technologies functionalities.

Starting from these elements, which delineate different scenarios, and through the adoption of the PACT method (Benyon, Turner, & Turner, 2005), it was possible to:

- Develop value proposition(s) where needs and gaps are matched with envisioned deliverable services in trial locations (basis for pilot scenario’s);
- Detect constraints that will characterize the future clinical/managerial/technological development of the digital solutions;
- Reflect over the overall feasibility of the proposed digital solutions, in order to progressively converge towards the one solution that will be used during the piloting phase.

All the aforementioned aspects were mapped onto the STOF framework and became useful for the various building blocks of the BMC framework of the paragraph §4.2 because they ensure the feasibility and the realism of the literature analysis’ findings.

3.2 Main Projects

This paragraph provides an overall view on three projects – found adopting the snowballing technique, as previously mentioned – in which digital service solutions are used to support patients with similar needs to those considered within DECI’s project.

Indeed, literature analysis was helpful to explore practical examples of digital services, giving a view of what are the key elements to consider when proceeding with the project. From this viewpoint, these projects can provide useful insights and information for DECI, since they deal with assistive solutions for people with dementia and/or MCI: all the documents adopted are listed in Table 1. The successes and the failures of these projects could facilitate the selection of the right approach.

Authors	Year	Title	Journal/Publisher	Project
Kerssens, C., Kumar, R., Adams, A. E., Knott, C. C., Matalenas, L., Sanford, J. A., & Rogers, W. A.	2015	Personalized Technology to Support Older Adults With and Without Cognitive Impairment Living at Home	American Journal of Alzheimer’s Disease and Other Dementias	Companion
Meiland, F. J., Reinersmann, A., Bergvall-Kareborn, B., Craig, D., Moelaert, F., Mulvenna, M. D., et al.	2007	COGKNOW Development and evaluation of an ICT-device for people with mild dementia	Studies in Health Technology and Informatics	Cogknow
Mulvenna, M. D., & Nugent, C. D.	2010	Supporting People with Dementia Using Pervasive Health Technologies	Springer London	Cogknow
Ógáin, E. N., & Mountain, K.	2015	Remember me	Nesta Impact Investments	Remember me

Table 1 - References related to projects

The three projects are the following:

- Companion;
- Cogknow;

- Remember me.

The objectives, methodology and the main results achieved by the projects are discussed in the following sub-paragraphs.

3.2.1 Companion

Following Kerssens et al. (2015), this project focuses on an already existing technology called “Companion”, which delivers physiological, non-drug interventions to patients with dementia in their homes to address individual symptoms and needs. The goal was to test the usability, feasibility, and adoption of Companion in home and community based setting. This project also focuses on the burden taken up by caregivers and on the reduction of their stress through technology. The achieved results provide important guidelines for designing and deploying home care technology.

This project was executed with a sample group of 7 patients. They were selected using the Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) and excluding scores below 10; the test was followed by phone interviews and screening of the patients. After the selection of patients, the life history of each one was used as an input in order to customise Companion for individuals and their caregivers. Once the device was personalized, it was placed at the patient’s home, such that they could easily access it.

The overall solution is a touch screen computer (no keyboard and no mouse) that delivers psychosocial interventions such as rich audiovisual programs (“shows”) that combine images, music, and messages from trusted individuals that are relevant and pleasing to the patient and, thus, engages him/her meaningfully and positively.

Even if the sample was small, what can be drawn from the study is that advanced technology can be personalized in many ways and technology-based interventions can support chronic condition management. Based on the results of the projects, it emerged that the personal motivation and the curiosity of the patient play key roles in technology usage. Although the goals of the project were met, the study points out that setting the right expectations is required in order to improve the independence of the patient and caregiver.

3.2.2 Cogknow

Following Meiland et al. (2007), the aim of Cogknow project is to address the needs of the people with dementia, in particular those affected by mild dementia. To this extent, the solution developed within the project aimed at supporting four cognitive areas: training memory, maintaining social contact, performing daily life and recreational activities and enhancing the feeling of safety. Workshops were carried out in three European countries. A side result of the workshops was a complete review of “state of the art” technological solutions.

Six people were involved in the project with respect to the severity of their dementia. Interviews and workshops were functional to identify user's needs. In a second phase of the project, a prototype was developed and evaluated with respect to three perspectives, namely human, technological and business factors.

Early in the project, the main needs of the users were focused based on the interviews conducted in 3 test sites. Four main solutions were selected that overall offer these main functionalities: support for pleasant activities, safety warnings, reminiscence through pictures. On a second stage of the project, an integrated system was realized combining all the aforementioned functions. Thus, the main functionalities were the following:

- Time Indication;
- Remotely configurable reminders;
- Music;
- Radio;
- Picture Dialing;
- Activity Assistance;
- House Alerts for safety;
- Mobile Navigation for going home.

3.2.3 Remember me

The paper of Ógáin & Mountain (2015) explores the role played by entrepreneurs, social innovators and investors in addressing the challenges of supporting people with dementia. In particular, the paper explains how these groups can provide: support exploring the possibilities of social care, access to non-pharmacological therapy and support with independent living. This paper also defines the two-fold role that investors could play:

- providing resources/funds to support the growth of products, tools and services;
- supporting the evaluation of these products, tools and services.

Authors illustrate how the investors can play a crucial role in funding projects, which are beneficial for the society and the health care of people with dementia. Various projects targeting different needs of the patients with dementia are listed, including some data such as size of the market, BM type and their impact. Final recommendations are given to investors with respect to marketplace.

The results are mainly related to the positive impact that investments can have in terms of quality of life improvement and support to local authorities whose funds are already under increasing pressure because of rising ageing population. Finally, the paper also shows market opportunities related to products and services that support people living with dementia and those who care for them.

4 Business Models Analysis

This chapter is related to the analysis of business models and it is divided into two main paragraphs. The first (§4.1) deals with the BM benchmarking conducted through the STOF framework: it is characterized by 4 sub-paragraphs related to the 4 domains of the aforementioned framework. The second sub-paragraph (§4.2) groups the findings of the literature analysis and the evidences related to the STOF framework into the 9 building blocks of the BMC framework. It is characterized by 9 sub-chapters related to the 9 building blocks of the framework.

4.1 Business Model Benchmark

The target of DECI project should be seen as a service innovation rather than pure technological development. Therefore, to define how the innovative service will be delivered in an economically viable way, the BM domains shall be discussed using the STOF framework. STOF framework describes a BM in terms of four interrelated domains (see Figure 4-1): Service, Technology, Organization and Finance.

Figure 4-1 STOF framework domains

Advantages of STOF method include its focus on the service analysis, and the fact that it takes into account the network of organizations involved while delivering the service (de Reuver, Bouwman, & Haaker, 2013). Even more, since DECI project aims to employ digital solutions for innovative service delivery, the significance of technology design aspects is placed within the STOF framework. Regarding the 4 domains:

- The service domain defines the service offering, its value proposition and the targeted market segment or, in terms of healthcare, the targeted customer or patient.
- The technology domain describes the technical design and functionality needed to deliver the service offering.
- The organization domain describes a structure of the diverse value network or-

ganized to create and provide the service offering.

- The finance domain describes the way a value network intends to ensure viable service offering in terms of revenue and cost, and the way risk, investments and revenues are divided among the various actors in a value network.

In this document, the BM benchmark is a comparison of the BM at each pilot site during or after the CCWs with stakeholders. The benchmarking process was grounded on the STOF framework domains. While these dimensions address the aspects of value delivery to the customers, the ‘customers’ should be regarded in a broad sense: from individuals and families to care providers.

The main inputs by pilot sites are highlighted per each building block of STOF framework and then summarized in order to synthesize the general inputs to the future DECI BM and to explain how the model can be supported financially. It provides various contributions that, together with the literature findings, allow to synthesize the various aspects of the 9 building blocks of the BMC.

4.1.1 Service Domain

While modelling the new BM using STOF method, launch of new services replacing the old services or adding new offerings on the top of the existing core ones comprise the service domain, which is the centre of the model.

To enable delivery of new services, the BM should propose the design of other BM components needed to be changed. Moreover, de Reuver et al (2013) argue that it is important to identify which technological, organizational and financial resources and skills are not needed when particular existing services are no longer provided.

The service domain also includes definition and/or extension of value proposition and target customer groups. According to Menko et al. (2013), value proposed should be aligned with the customers’ needs and perception of value. Moreover, the BM can create value for the customers, but not necessarily be of appropriate value to other actors of the network. In such case, the BM would not be viable.

The following paragraphs represent the BM inputs generated by participants of the CCWs in each DECI pilot Country. In §4.1.1.5 the information is synthesised into the main insights for further BM development within DECI project context.

4.1.1.1. Italy

The CCW led by Fondazione Don Carlo Gnocchi ONLUS, Fondazione Politecnico di Milano and Roessingh Research and Development resulted in a number of **service insights and requirements**:

- Service should be designed around patient and family needs;
- Service should be co-created in partnership with patients and family members;
- Service should be integrated among all related subjects;
- All related subjects should be considered and heard for service improvement;

- Service needs to provide immediate responses to subjects in need;
- Service needs to include emergency notifications;
- Management of unforeseen events is critical for elderly people with MCI diagnosis;
- Patient monitoring service should be automated where possible;
- Service needs to be least time-consuming possible;
- The value proposition should include as much as possible all-inclusive solutions to facilitate the support of care activities;
- In order to ensure trusted and informed service delivery, timely and constant information update and alignment within the service users are vital.

The two envisioned scenarios defined in the CCW report – informative platform and all-inclusive automatic monitoring – comprise a number of service elements and perceived value for end users.

Informative platform scenario outlines the following service elements:

- Manual input of data and information regarding patient care;
- Information and data should be accessible for all the relevant stakeholders;
- Constant update of information and data, analysis and presentation of trends.

The service value in this scenario lies in the constant availability of updated information that supports and informs care activities and might improve internal coordination between the care network.

All-inclusive automatic monitoring scenario outlines the following summarized service elements:

- Automatic data acquisition regarding patient status and environment;
- Emergency notification resulting in aid activities.

The service value in this scenario lies in the monitoring capabilities of the solutions, which enable an increase in patient safety, independency and automation facilitating the care process.

4.1.1.2. Spain

The CCW led by Hospital Universitario de Getafe resulted in the identification of **service benefits** when using DECI platform:

- Patient benefits: maintaining independence, autonomy and self-reliance. Longer stay at own home instead of moving to a relative's home or being institutionalized. Increased interactions and improved mood through exercise programs;
- Informal caregiver and family benefits: reduced stress and burden of disease, potential financial saving when illness is delayed;
- Social and health care professional benefits: work efficiency, improved patient monitoring including more possibilities to face-to-face interaction, enabled illness control and prevention due to increased data access, timeliness and variety.

4.1.1.3. Sweden

The CCW led by Chalmers university of Technology and Skaraborg hospital resulted in the **service insights and requirements**:

- Service needs to provide easily installable, intuitive and user-friendly digital solutions;
- Service should include automatic data sending to care providers' systems, relatives or other related parties;
- Service should include warning systems, notifications and reminders;
- Service should include tools for visualization;
- Service should include easy-to-handle reports for monitoring;
- Service should provide real-time data for timely decisions;
- Service should enable real-time response for staff and resource inclusion, also for staff allocation and advance planning, scheduling and route optimization.

The integration of digital systems of different care providers is crucial.

4.1.1.4. Israel

The CCW led by Maccabi Health Centre resulted in the **service benefits** when using DECI platform:

- Potential process efficiency and time saving;
- Enabled patients' self-assessment and follow-up as well as self treatment;
- Enabled patient-medical staff interaction;
- Enabled usage of increased set of patient data through self-monitoring and patient management solution;
- Improved follow-up and monitoring through new exercising and training tools;
- Improved response and prevention of deterioration and hospitalization through alerts from the system.

More data might result in better tools for assessment and treatment and also for standardization of care and risk management.

4.1.1.5. Synthesis

The **value proposition** highlighted by inputs from CCWs in partner countries contains a number of key reasons why DECI service is likely to provide substantial value:

- Increase in well-being of MCI affects individuals through longer stay at home rather than moving to the hospital. Better physical and cognitive health through exercise and training;
- Higher social inclusion through interactions with staff and other individuals;
- Self-monitoring is a next step in the improved healthcare of MCI affected individuals. Where possible, the individual should be enabled and encouraged to take responsibility over his or her own health status. This can be achieved through the possibilities of self-monitoring;

- The potential arising from data collection is significant, as it may result in new ideas regarding care, tools, more information, and possibilities to assess and make informed decisions.

During the synthesis of partners' inputs, the major **common patterns of service elements** in future BM have been looked for. Among the valuable insights, the most prominent are the following:

- Personalization should be the key attribute to DECI service. Enabled by ICT solutions, DECI platform should offer decision-making system through enhanced data collection and achieved through remote patient monitoring and interaction;
- Integration and data sharing are among the key pillars of DECI service. It should be implemented among all the related subjects and institutions within care networks to the maximum possible extent.

Automation is of particular interest to the care providers. Data exchange automation might bring a number of benefits, such as process efficiency, time savings, timely information provision which enables immediate response to the patient needs. Moreover, emergency and unpredicted situations can be managed easier through automated warnings and notifications.

4.1.2 Technology Domain

To implement the service offering, a matching technical functionality is required. Menko et al. (2013) define few variables to this domain: technical architecture, network accessibility, devices and applications. System security, accessibility, ease of usage and integration are the key factors for this domain.

The technology domain embraces critical design issues on various levels of the technology architecture: infrastructure, platforms, applications and software. Changes in the technology choices and new technology introduction may impact the service offering and the cost structure of the service.

4.1.2.1 Italy

The CCW led by Fondazione Don Carlo Gnocchi ONLUS, Fondazione Politecnico di Milano and Roessingh Research and Development resulted in a number of **essential elements** of technology domain per 2 scenarios:

Informative platform scenario:

- Enabled activity reporting by patient, registering data by him/herself, by caregivers, doctors, geriatricians or family members;
- Caregivers and other actors can access, edit and retrieve stored information, where and when appropriate;
- Information content has to be constantly updated according to patients' characteristics;

- Remote data access and mobility is the key opportunity in the DECI platform, therefore tablets, smartphones and even patients' home television can be treated as viable channels for end-users' information access;
- The system has to be adapted to the actual recipients' capabilities.

All-inclusive automatic monitoring scenario:

- Acquisition of data from monitoring devices, either placed on the patient's body or inside his/her living environment;
- Supervision activities mostly check if quantitative parameters exceed a certain set of pre-determined boundaries, therefore highlighting a situation of potential danger;
- Notification/alert functionality is needed to signal the need for assistance, according to the nature of the emergency.

Additional insights regarding needs for technology are as follows:

- Non-invasiveness of the technology, hidden within daily devices, when possible;
- Visible technology needs to be easily approachable and easy-to-use, especially in hazardous situations;
- Information management module needs to be able to gather data from all sources, and present it in the user-friendly and easily understandable format.

The envisioned scenarios can integrate multiple technological solutions already available in the DECI project: from **smart watches for fall detection** as part of the all-inclusive automatic monitoring scenario (patient monitoring input), to **web-based exercise systems** within the informative platform scenario (information provision output), to a **patient management system**, a potential integration solution between the two scenarios (activities recording and overall information management).

4.1.2.2 Spain

The CCW led by Hospital Universitario de Getafe resulted in a number of **essential elements** of the technology domain regarding online platform:

- System should be easy to use and should not require patients to enter a great amount of data. Touch screens and voice input could be appropriate solutions along with ordinary key-board based options;
- Patients' abilities as well as disabilities should be considered (vision, hearing and touch);
- System should be able to gather explicit and implicit (using sensors) information about the patient, inputted by the patient or by the informal caregiver;
- Patient/caregiver/health or social care professional should be able to create an agenda/diary of activities: daily activities, favourite/common places, medication, etc.;
- Patients should be able to receive reminders about the scheduled activities;

- System should enable patients to communicate with health and social care professionals: to send questions and report symptoms or changes in behaviour;
- Patients should be able to receive educational material about the disease and about the social benefits available (for the patient and for the informal caregiver);
- Patients should be enabled to receive cognitive training through the system;
- System should allow to perform tests to assess the cognitive status of the patient;
- System should allow to create and access a protocol for diagnosing, treating and advising patients. The protocol should comprise of the diagnosis, treatment, evolution, symptoms and events and patient monitoring data captured by sensors;
- System should allow communication among all the stakeholders and social and health care professionals and between social and health care professionals and patients;
- System should allow professionals to write, read, edit and delete information about the patient, such as diagnosis and treatment;
- System should be able to send messages and alerts, especially to the ‘case manager’ or ‘case tutor’.

Wearable devices are preferable, since it can gather information about the patient, and has communication capabilities. Patients with CI may forget to take their mobile phones, etc., therefore a wearable device can be a solution for reminders.

4.1.2.3 Sweden

The CCW led by Chalmers university of Technology and Skaraborg hospital resulted in a number of **essential elements** of technology domain per 2 envisioned scenarios:

Integrated information system scenario:

- **Interoperability** should be assured to facilitate data exchange and communication, to view and edit aggregated data real-time synchronizing data updates between platform and caregivers` systems based on pre-agreed rules;
- **System security** addresses the issues such as privacy, access and data management authorizations;
- **Remote access** to the system should be established so that the individuals, relatives and other relevant parties would be able to add/update the data over individual’s situation;
- **Data entering and editing** authorizations should be reasonably limited;
- To enable the **shared decision-making**, two aspects are essential: common routines for data management between all of the involved parties and user-friendly visualization tools that would be intuitive and easily understandable for the users;

- System should **support planning** activities, including scheduling and planning of human and tangible resources;
- **Notifications and other means of communication** between different care providers and individuals and their relatives should be established.

Patient monitoring system scenario

- The system should be able to **acquire data from various devices** (e.g. mobile phone or watch) that collect individual's data;
- It is essential to ensure that the ICT solutions that enable the monitoring and are used by the individual with MCI, are **user-friendly**, highly intuitive and easy to handle, and appropriate considering the diagnosis and personal abilities;
- **Remote access** by all the needed actors within the care system and process ensures informed decisions and provides notifications and alarms that enable timely response to help the individual;
- **System security and ethics** should be considered for data transmission. Secure measures with minimized manual or anonymous interventions should be taken into account. The data should be visible only to the authorized users.

Additional insights regarding needs for technology are as follows:

- Platform on which the integrated and patient management systems would be built should capture the data from disparate sources such as phones, wearable and data measuring devices and Internet of Things and provide end-users a holistic and real-time view of the patient's health;
- 3rd-party systems by caregivers, hospitals or other interested parties need to be integrated or otherwise connected;
- Workflow of the processes concerning integrated care should be implemented;
- Performance monitoring and reporting functions should be among critical elements in the system;
- For quality improvement reasons, claims management module might be considered.

For the patient management system, the user interface of the software should be highly user-friendly for manual data inputs and ensure ethical handling of patients' data through authorized access and data management options.

4.1.2.4 Israel

The CCW led by Maccabi Health Centre resulted in a number of **essential elements** of technology domain:

- System should include the treatment plan, tasks for the various care providers, alerts, ability for follow-up and should be integrated to the Electronic Health Record;

- The system should enable connection and integrated care with organizations/care providers outside healthcare such as social care, day care centres and volunteer organizations in the community;
- There is a need for solution like a walking test which can be placed inside the clinics and random patients can perform self assessment for walking stability (risk of falls). The data would be transferred to doctor for further assessment and treatment and would enable large screening of the population and early detection;
- Self-assessment, self-reporting and self-treatment enabling functionalities are highly desired. It should help follow patient's clinical parameters and treatment plan;
- Online cognitive training tools and educational materials should be accessible to the patient;
- System should store information about the cognitive training performed, scores, improvement;
- System should alert patient about his/her upcoming tasks;
- System should be adapted to the elderly population and designed in a user-friendly way.

4.1.2.5 Synthesis

Partners from Italy and Sweden envisioned 2 similar **technology scenarios** each:

- Informative platform scenario (Italy) and integrated information system scenario (Sweden) are designed for enabled information exchange and input by all the stakeholders;
- The all-inclusive automatic monitoring scenario (Italy) and patient monitoring system scenario (Sweden) are designed for acquisition of patient data and notifications and alerts signalling hazardous events.

The **functionalities** highlighted by inputs from the CCWs in partner countries contain a number of key aspects identified as some of the major requirements to the DECI platform. They include:

- Self-assessment and self-management;
- Adaptability to individual capabilities to manage the system and enter data;
- Online cognitive training;
- Online patient status tracking/control and possibility to see the treatment protocol, test results;
- Remote access to the system and data;
- Additional educational material within the access by patient and family;
- Alerts, reminders and notifications;
- Manual data input and view possibility by all parties;
- Enabled communication between all the parties of the integrated network;
- Enabled connection to the system by informal caregivers;
- Interoperability;

- Ability to gather information from external sources, systems and devices.

For external devices (wearable devices, smart-phones, etc.) the following key requirements were identified:

- Technology/devices should be non-invasive;
- Easy-to-use and adapted to the individual capabilities;
- Hidden where possible without interaction with the patient;
- Able to collect and transmit the data to the system.

It is interesting to note that desired functionalities by stakeholders highly repeat between the partner countries. On the one hand, the repetition could happen due to trends and a worldwide need of the healthcare transformation towards more personalized and automated solutions. On another hand, there is a likelihood that the insights could have been inspired by moderator's presentations of the DECI technology.

To conclude, there is a match between partner countries' expectations of technology functionality in future BM and in the DECI platform, which will facilitate the design of the future business models supported by DECI platform at the partner sites.

4.1.3 Organization Domain

The organizational domain is mainly focused around the system's actors, roles, network structure and its governance, as well as the reduction of network's complexity. The focus is on the multi-actor value network required to create and provide the service offering (Menko et al., 2013).

4.1.3.1 Italy

The CCW led by Fondazione Don Carlo Gnocchi ONLUS, Fondazione Politecnico di Milano and Roessingh Research and Development resulted in a number of **insights for organisational model**.

The care activities have to be adapted to the patient's characteristics and needs. Less standardized and more personalized services are the pathways to the desired flexibility.

The organization within the **informative platform scenario** relates to the caregivers, doctors and family members within the perimeter of an information platform, thus soliciting alignment and informal cooperation among the involved subjects for planning and execution of care activities. The platform itself works as coordination resource and patient information can be accessed by the aforementioned actors who keep their traditional roles. Ownership of the platform could belong to the case manager (description of the role of case manager is provided below), or service provider.

The **all-inclusive automatic monitoring scenario** has a smaller impact on organizational aspects and mostly relates to the management of adequate reaction to the potentially hazardous situations. The key actor is a patient who is monitored with a passive approach. Once notification is received by care providers, appropriate actions need to be coordinated among relevant caregivers, family members and a case manager (description of the role of case manager is provided below). Ownership of the devices and notification system could belong to the case manager or service provider.

The new role of **Case manager** is the centre of the envisioned future organisational model. Case manager would act as a coordinator of care activities and information management. He/she would work as the main person in charge to provide responses to patients and their families, having a complete view on each patient's clinical status, cognitive evolution and general information. The management of the informative platform could be dedicated to the Case manager or external service provider. Moreover, the ownership of the devices and the resulting notification system can be bestowed upon the Case Manager or the service provider.

The informal **cooperation** between different roles through **informative platform** (see Technology domain) should result in common access, planning and organization of care activities. However, the standard services, such as emergency could be organized as usual.

In the hazardous events, actions need to be organised and coordinated among potential notification recipients. These include all caregivers, family members and eventually a Case Manager; the **informal alignment** between these subjects grants an adequate emergency response.

4.1.3.2 Spain

The co-creation workshop led by Hospital Universitario de Getafe resulted in a number of **insights for organisational model**. 4 main groups of actors are envisioned in the socio-sanitary value chain:

- Patients and informal caregivers as service receivers;
- Health Care Technologies' providers include:
 - Hardware providers: companies owning the sensors;
 - Software providers: companies in charge of creating and maintaining the on-line platform;
 - Content providers: companies providing the training material.
- Health and Social Service Providers:
 - In public settings:
 - Family doctors and nurses in Primary Care Centers;
 - Specialized care, located at the Hospital.
 - In private settings:

- Family doctors and nurses;
- Specialized care.
- Social services:
 - Public social services provided by the municipality (day centres, etc.);
 - Private social services (private nursing homes, etc.).
- Paying authorities
 - The Regional Ministry of Health manages Primary and Specialized Care;
 - The Hospital Manager;
 - The Municipality provides patients with social services;
 - Private companies offering care and social services;
 - NGO's such as Foundations and Patient Associations provide patients and their families with education, support, training workshops, etc.

The most important role within the care network will be performed by the '**case manager**', who will be the main contact person that will carry out the follow-up of the patient. The 'case manager' will have special privileges within the DECI system.

4.1.3.3 Sweden

The CCW led by Chalmers University of Technology and Skaraborg Hospital resulted in a number of **insights for organisational model**:

- Integration-related dominant body such as the **network management or governance team** with representatives from each caregiver. The team should determine which new organisations should be included in the network, set the rules and monitor its compliance. The body should also gather local ideas and issues and set the principles, values and procedures for the care process to act upon. The network management team should also encourage quality improvement initiatives and empower each member of the network staff to take part in delivering the best value to the customers.
- **Case manager** (dementia nurse) should be assigned a critical role to coordinate all care activities in collaboration with Aid assistance coordinator throughout the care process lifecycle.

Responsibilities should be clear when it comes to budget allocation to the care process, prescription of medical aids (e.g. a wheelchair), responsibility over data correctness, patient safety incidents, and reliability of the technology.

4.1.3.4 Israel

The CCW led by Maccabi Health Centre resulted in a number of insights for organisational model.

Case manager (GP) is a central role that would coordinate the treatment and follow-up using the computerized system.

In addition to the case manager - the doctor, there should be a coordinator, a nurse that are more available and more focused on the specific treatment and can also coordinate the interfaces between healthcare and community (non clinical aspects).

4.1.3.5 Synthesis

During the synthesis of partners' inputs, the major common patterns of organizational and network composition in the future business model have been looked for. Among the valuable insights, the most prominent are the followings.

The organization of the roles and responsibilities around care activities was approached through **multiple strategies by the project partners**. The Italian partner defined the key organizational aspects based on the envisioned system scenarios (specifically – informative platform scenario and all-inclusive automatic monitoring scenario) thus providing a clear vision of the potential composition of key pillars of the organizational care model. The Spanish partner defined the key groups of actors in the socio-sanitary value network, from patients to the paying authorities. The Swedish partner envisioned the organization of the care network through the lens of the pyramid: support and maintenance level, implementation level and management body. The partner from Israel focused on the case manager role as the main organizational innovation.

The need of the role as **Case manager** was identified at all four partner countries during the co-creation workshops. Acting as the central component of the model would be the key responsibility of a Case manager. This role is envisioned to be the overall coordinator of the patient's care process lifecycle. Moreover, patient information management would be another important responsibility of a Case manager. However, different sites suggest different personnel in the current care models to be assigned as Case manager (Sweden – dementia nurse, Israel – general practitioner).

Network governance and management team is an insight provided by Swedish partner. The role of such body would be to determine which new organisations should be included in the network, set the rules and monitor its compliance. Such team would consist of the representatives from each caregiver in the network.

Informality and cooperation among the caregivers within the network was stressed as the important aspect of the organization (Italian partner).

Organizations outside routine care network, such as **non-governmental organizations and relevant associations** were emphasized as important actors in the future care model for MCI affected individuals (Spanish partner).

4.1.4 Financial Domain

In order to support the other domains, finance plays a critical role and enables other domains. Finance domain describes the way a value network intends to generate

revenues from a particular service offering (Menko et al., 2013), cost structure, investment needed and associated risks.

4.1.4.1 Italy

The CCW led by Fondazione Don Carlo Gnocchi ONLUS, Fondazione Politecnico di Milano and Roessingh Research and Development resulted in a number of **insights for economic model**:

- **Costs and cost structure**, which will include personnel costs, devices implementation and usage, data storage and management; the business model will have to take into consideration which subjects will be addressed for each cost;
- **Investments**, which will include initial expenditures enabling the correct deployment of the service and of all the underlining components that support service provision throughout its life cycle;
- **Revenues** and revenue streams, which will include all revenue aspects starting from the definition of a revenue structure balancing costs and based on regional financings, families' availabilities and national refunds;
- **Risks**, which includes a financial-focused evaluation of potential hazards that could negatively impact on the revenue streams and, in general, the economic perspectives of the service.

It is therefore possible to draw general considerations on the two depicted scenarios according to the four STOF financial variables:

- The **informative platform scenario**:
 - **Costs** include platform maintenance and data storage, management of remote-based accesses and costs related to information provision at patients' and family members' home;
 - **Investments** include the initial set up and configuration of the platform and the arrangement of all remote-base accesses;
 - **Revenues** for this specific service might derive from regional or national funds, or be connected to hospitals' innovation initiatives, should the solution be pivoted around and healthcare company;
 - **Risks** include low user acceptance and resulting low usage of the platform, therefore impairing its effectiveness; similarly, a change in regional or national policies and priorities might result in diminishing funds;
- The **all-inclusive automatic monitoring solution**:
 - **Costs** include the management and maintenance of the monitoring devices, as well as the maintenance of the notification network for the acquisition of alerts;
 - **Investments** include the initial monitoring devices acquisition, installation and eventual customization, as well as the implementation of a notification network for emergency alerts

- **Revenues** could be envisioned with an hybrid approach, having families acquire the monitoring components for the supervision of their relatives, with the economic support of regional or national authorities;
- **Risks** are mostly connected with the incorrect usage of devices from the patient, which might result in device damage; a patient might also refuse to use a device that he/she perceives as alien; as for the aforementioned scenario, a change in regional or national policies and priorities might result in diminishing economic support towards families.

4.1.4.2 Spain

The CCW led by Hospital Universitario de Getafe resulted in a number of **insights for economic model**.

Within the Spanish public healthcare system, it is not possible to charge patients any payments or co-payments. The implementation of a solution like the DECI platform in the public health sector would be based on the **reduction of costs** associated to the improvement provided by DECI, and would be financed by the public administration, specifically by the Regional Health Ministry of Madrid.

Set up costs, such as purchase of sensors, deployment of the online platform or training of specialized nurses could be financed via public procurement programs, such as the Pre-Commercial Public Procurement Program of the National Health Ministry (to acquire hardware equipment and/or software) or innovation programs such as FIS grants. Maintenance costs should be financed by the Regional Health Ministry or the Hospitals. The Municipality can also finance aspects of the system, such as the procurement of hardware sensors.

Private health care providers can adopt a very different strategy, selling patients and their families a 'set-up' package including the sensors and charging them a monthly fee to use the system.

4.1.4.3 Sweden

The co-creation workshop led by Chalmers University of Technology and Skaraborg Hospital resulted in a number of **insights for the economic model**.

To build the business model according to the scenario defined, **financial resources should be increasingly focused upstream towards health maintenance at the early stages of illness**. When the focus is placed in the early stages of the illness, the whole system is likely to win through cost savings due to reduced number of hospital visits and mitigated patient safety risks. Resource efficiency could also be attained through planning process. Resource allocation should be informed and need-based.

There is also a need to pay attention to the prevention costs which are usually much lesser than reactive cost.

The STOF methodology frames finance within cost, investment and risks, revenue and risk dimensions.

- The main areas of **investment and risks** include acquisition of ICT solutions, the set-up of the platform and connectedness with the remote devices, building of the care network, and necessary staff attraction to the regions and staff competence development. To manage the investment risks that can arise due to uncertainty of user acceptance, the pilot activities involving ICT solutions should be performed prior to the actual full-scale roll-out of the services and purchase of the devices.
- The major **cost** areas are maintenance of the ICT devices and IT platform, cost to be incurred to manage the care network and organise best-practice sharing and learning networks for learning loops to emerge to make the change happen; patient and relatives' management related cost for information provision and fast response.
- The areas of **revenue** dimension include governmental funds (regional and national), and in some cases – payments by patients and families for specific investment needed for individual's wellbeing.

4.1.4.4 Israel

No info from the CCW held in this Country for this domain of the STOF framework.

4.1.4.5 Synthesis

The **economic model** highlighted by inputs from co-creation workshops in partner countries addresses a number of key aspects to the economic feasibility consideration when implementing the DECI platform and future organizational model. It includes:

- The approach towards **cost** perspective showed variation between countries. Spain emphasised expectation and focus to the reduction of cost through implementation of DECI platform. Meanwhile, Sweden highlighted importance to move the expenditure towards upstream activities to prevent progression of the illness, thus preventing a higher future cost. There is also a need to pay attention to the prevention costs which are usually much lesser than reactive cost. **The key areas of cost** were identified as: personnel costs, devices implementation and usage, data storage and management, maintenance of the notification network for the acquisition of alerts, management of remote-based accesses and costs related to information provision at patients' and family members' home.
- **Revenue** is expected to receive from national and regional funding, as well as private investments through selling to patients and their families a 'set-up' package including the sensors and charging them a monthly fee to use the system (al-

though, in some countries such set-up package could possibly be covered by municipalities).

- The main **investment** expected to occur is related to the actual implementation of the new organizational model and services, and the installation of the DECI platform, as well as purchasing external devices to be used. A concern has also been put on the competence development of the staff.
- The key **risks** associated to the envisioned service, model and DECI platform is patient resistance to actually engage in using the ICT solutions and a possible low user acceptance thus block the potential benefits and effectiveness of the system.

4.1.5 Concluding Discussion

The CCWs in the four countries resulted in valuable insights for the future BM of DECI. In summary, patterns, and important similarities and differences using the STOF framework were identified from the results of the four executed CCWs in the partner countries. The patterns are important to consider in the future development of the DECI project, and in the construction of final innovative BMs.

In the STOF framework, *the service domain* defines the service offering, its value proposition and the targeted market segment or, in terms of healthcare, the targeted customer or patient group. Discussions regarding the value proposition of services based on DECI-platform revealed that stakeholders' needs and expectations are coherent with intended DECI project goals. The well-being of MCI-affected individuals could be improved through service construction around physical and cognitive health enhancement, social inclusion, self-monitoring and preventive actions informed by data collected through the platform. Some key service aspects identified throughout the partner countries are ICT-enabled personalization of care, integration and data sharing among care network, and automation of data exchange. This can result in a number of benefits to a number of stakeholders, however this should not be taken for granted.

The *technology domain* describes the technical design and functionality needed to deliver the service offering. Two types of technology scenarios were identified and could serve as options for the technology development in the DECI project. First, the information system scenario which would enable information exchange between stakeholders. Second, the monitoring system scenario which would enable alerts and notifications based on patient data. An integration of the two scenarios could possibly serve as a third thinkable scenario. Many potential functionalities in the systems were identified in the four workshops. In this regard, implications on the future work of the DECI project is that a conscious selection of functionalities is needed.

The *organization domain* describes a structure of the diverse value network organized to create and provide the service offering. In summary, multiple strategies were identified in the co-creation workshops to manage the organisational domain. This could be due to the reason that the organisational set-up differs between the countries. Hence, it can be argued that each country needs to find its appropriate organisational design in order to manage the implementation and management of the developed business model and the connected technology. The need of the role as Case manager was however identified at all four partner countries, and should hence be an important organisational implication.

The *finance domain* describes the way a value network intends to ensure viable service offering in terms of revenue and cost, and the way risk, investments and revenues are divided among the various actors in a value network. Key areas of cost were identified, and the areas can include costs for personnel, device implementation and usage, data storage and management, maintenance of the notification network for the acquisition of alerts, management of remote-based accesses and costs related to information provision at patients' and family members' home. However, the cost areas and amount depend on which intervention is performed. Moreover, costs are likely to occur when actually implementing (or developing existing) business models. Revenue can possibly be received from national and regional funding, as well as from private investments through vending technology to patients and their families. For the finance domain, it can be concluded that one needs to carefully monitor the cost issue of the intervention and consider possibilities of a total cost reduction and moving costs upstream in the care process.

4.2 Business Model Synthesis

This paragraph categorizes the findings of the literature search and the evidences related to the STOF framework (Chapter 3 and Paragraph 4.1 respectively) into the 9 Building Blocks described by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010).

It is composed by 9 sub-paragraphs related to the 9 building blocks of the aforementioned framework and it is characterized by the adoption of **two lenses**. The first one considers the viewpoint of the end-user of the solution, while the second one takes into accounts all the actors that are in charge of realizing, managing and delivering the service or part of it.

Each sub-paragraph is completed with the following elements:

- the **introductory section** related to the definitions and categorizations provided by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010);
- all **literature's findings** and results from the **Co-Creation Workshops** (CCWs) that can be framed through a specific building block.

4.2.1 Customer Segments

The customer segment is the main element of any BM: in order to better satisfy the customers, the company can group them into distinct segments with common needs, behaviors or attributes. The BM can have one or several customer segments and the relative size of the customer segments can also vary from small to large.

The organization must take a key decision about which customer segments to involve and which customer segments to pass by: once undertaken the decision, it is possible to design a BM around the strong understanding of specific customer needs.

In general, a group of customers represents different customer segments if they satisfy the following criterion (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010, p. 20):

- Their needs require and justify a distinct offer;
- They are reached through different distribution channels;
- They require different types of relationships;
- They have substantially different profits;
- They are willing to pay for different aspects of the offer.

Based on the size and the characteristic of the customers, the customer segment building block of the BM can be broadly classified into these following types of segments (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010):

- **Mass market:** the BM does not distinguish between different customer segments. The BM, and in particular the value proposition, channels and the customer relationship, focus just on one large group of customers with similar needs and features.
- **Niche market:** the BM is addressed to specific, specialized customer segments; then the value proposition, distribution channels and customer relationships are all adapted to the specific requirement.
- **Segmented:** the customer base in this model is distributed into various segments. The segmentation is based on the varying needs of the customers. The different segments may have some characteristics in common but value proposition, distribution channels and the customer relationships are different for the various segments in the BM.
- **Diversified:** in this type of classification the customer base is split into two customer segments with very different needs and problems.
- **Multi sided platforms:** the customer segments are independent of each other. The value proposition, distribution channels and the customer relationships are different and unrelated to each other.

Taking into account the end user – thus the patient – perspective, literature suggests that the number of customer segments with respect to dementia and cognitive impairment is very high, such as: patients with MCI and early stages of dementia, patients with MCI, patients with dementia, patients with cognitive impairment, pa-

tients with Alzheimer's disease, older adults living at home, mild dementia and dementia with physiological distress. Nevertheless, further discussion with clinicians involved in the project pointed out that the needs of the customer with physiological distress cannot be very well defined because they are hard to quantify, thus the BM cannot be built around them.

Keeping in mind all these points, the main customer segments which were selected are the following:

- Patients with dementia;
- Patients with MCI.

The needs of each segments are distinct but it should be noted that MCI in some cases progresses further into dementia. Thus, the base needs of the customers are basically the same but, as dementia is an advancement of MCI, the needs of demented patients are much more complex and the customer relation are completely different.

Petersen (2009) – confirming what already discussed within partners' discussion at CCWs – pointed out that people with MCI can be further sub grouped into the following:

- Amnesic (memory impairment);
- Non Amnesic (structural impairment).

Furthermore, it was learnt from the CCWs that the needs of the patients with amnesic and non-amnesic MCI are quite different: most of the technologies that would be provided to the patients with MCI will prove completely useless to patients with amnesic MCI, as most of the technologies do not deal with memory related disorders.

Whereas non-amnesic patients are the ones with no memory related problems, they do need assistance with the day-to-day activities. Non-amnesic MCI affects the ability to make sound decisions, judge the time or sequence of steps needed to complete a complex task, or visual perception.

Considering these elements, three customer segments should be considered when drafting the BM:

- Patients with dementia;
- Patients with Amnesic MCI (a-MCI);
- Patients with Non Amnesic MCI (na-MCI).

Due to the high level of personalization that digital service solutions require, these customer segments cannot be classified as "mass market". They are characterized by needs that often overlap among segments. Therefore, also "diversified" and "multi sided platforms" categories do not fit the features of these customer segments.

Only the categories of "niche market" and "segmented" are coherent with the characteristics of these segments because of the aforementioned specificity of needs for

a restricted population of customers and because of some commonalities among segments (for further details §4.2.2).

From the overall system's perspective, the two segments that are responsible for the care process are the following:

- Healthcare specialists/providers;
- Healthcare organizations/facilities.

They are both characterized by the need of coordination, information integration, quality and efficiency (for further details §4.2.2). However, they differ widely from one to the other because of organizational aspects and investment capacity.

4.2.2 Value Propositions

The value proposition can be defined as the reason why a customer chooses one company products and services – both aspects that create value for a specific customer segment, solving their problems and satisfying their needs. The value proposition is an aggregation of benefits that a company offers its customers.

While deciding the value proposition for the company, the main questions that should be asked are the following (Osterwalder and Pigneur 2010):

- What value do we deliver to the customers?
- Which one of our customers' problems are we helping to solve?
- Which customer needs are we satisfying?
- Which bundles of products and services are we offering to each customer segment?

The different value propositions which can be offered to the customers are the following:

- **Newness:** to satisfy a new set of needs, that weren't perceived before because there were no similar offers.
- **Performance:** the existing product or the services can be improved upon thus creating value.
- **Customization:** developing products and services tailored to specific needs of the customers.
- **"Getting the job done":** the product or the service supports the customer in doing his job.
- **Design:** in the consumer electronics industry, also the design can be a particularly important part of the value proposition.
- **Brand/status:** the value is mainly related to the brand and the status related to it.
- **Price:** it is specific for price-sensitive segments and it is related to a low price offering of comparable value.
- **Cost reduction:** the product or the service supports the customer in reducing his costs.

- **Risk reduction:** lowering the risk connected with the purchasing of the product or service offered.
- **Accessibility:** overcoming the previous limitations that denied access to the product or service offered.
- **Convenience/usability:** offering user-friendly products or services.

From the point of view of the patient, what affects the value proposition of any digital service is the severity of the illness. The worse is the severity of the illness, the higher the interaction patient-technology is compromised and the more a caregiver is needed to act as an interface between technology and patient. Patients with Amnesic MCI, non-amnesic MCI or mild dementia are characterized by various needs to be addressed; some of them can be mainly related to one of these pathologies while others could be common for many of them.

A tool adopted to assess the various and specific needs is the Camberwell Assessment of Need for the Elderly model (CANE) (Reynolds et al., 2000), that is implemented within WP1. Results of the assessment allow understanding that patients with dementia have more care needs than MCI patients. Furthermore, it emerged that needs concerning drugs management, memory impairment, looking after home and psychological distress are ordinary for MCI patients. At a higher level of detail, self-care, money management, mobility, behavioral disturbances and looking after home are more common for na-MCI than a-MCI patients. Furthermore, the needs of money management, drugs management, memory impairment, looking after home, self-care, mobility, psychological distress, behavioral disturbances and continence are common needs for patients with Mild Dementia.

In order to address the variety of needs of the patient segments, different kinds of solutions and services were identified from the literature analysis and from the Business Model Benchmark (§4.1). Overall, digital solutions address different purposes synthesized as follows:

- **Detect early symptoms of dementia:** MCI generally progresses into dementia thus the early detection of dementia through digital media can be helpful in the early treatment of the patient. An approach is the recording of daily activities and sleeping. Following König et al. (2005) one of the symptoms of the patients with dementia and MCI is “stress”. The aforementioned authors discussed the possibility of a technology that could assess the linguistic capabilities – thus the words spoken by a person – detecting certain “stress words” uttered by the patient and their frequency of utterance. Through the analysis of various elements (e.g. vocal reaction time, amount of silence, semantic fluency, etc.) it is possible to diagnose the pathology and distinguish between MCI and Alzheimer’s Disease.
- **Support and stimulate orientation and memory:** the patients with dementia tend to forget the details of their location and their friends and families. A study conducted by Kerssens et al. (2015) explore the support of rich audio visual pro-

grams (Companion project §3.2.1), that are personal photos, videos and audio messages provided through constant reminders from a digital device - could give to patients in order to remember their location and their family members. This solution is suitable for people with dementia, MCI and elderly people since it takes into account physical limitations of the patient (e.g. visual impairments) and it provides a coherent output (e.g. pictures automatically enlarged) thus resulting to be effective. Likewise, also Meiland et al. (2007) emphasizes the use of technology to provide pleasure and comfort to the patient, supporting his memory during the daily activities (e.g. turn on the television and find the right TV channel).

- **Develop routines through reminders:** dementia patients have no memory of the tasks they have to carry out, thus they require reminders for their day-to-day activities. Digital solutions that provide reminders are suitable for people with dementia, MCI and elderly people (Kerssens et al., 2015) but their effectiveness depends on how well they are designed and integrate within the daily routines of the patient. The effectiveness pertains to the fact that the wrong positioning (in terms of time for the reminder and/or of space for the device) could have a negative effect on the utilization of the solution therefore on the health of the patient. The mapping of the various activities conducted by the patient is propaedeutic to the choice related to the positioning of the reminder/device. Another way to help patients to develop routines avoiding confusion about days and dates could be the use of an electronic calendar with functionalities of reminder (Meiland et al., 2007).
- **Enhance the feeling of safety:** digital devices could assure support to the patient by remembering him/her important activities, supporting him/her finding objects, supporting him/her calling caregivers (family members and/or friends) in case of need (Meiland et al., 2007; Mulvenna & Nugent, 2010). Technology prevents patient from experiencing anxiety or dangers (Meiland et al., 2007). Such a solution, suitable for people with dementia, is tested within the Cogknow project. As an example, the solution signals that the patient is forgetting something at home like the keys or the mobile phone or warns him/her to close the door. Furthermore, if the patient forgot the location of the mobile phone, he/she can touch a picture of the device at the Cogknow station and a buzzer sound conducts him/her to the mobile phone. The simpler the technology the better, since usually this kind of patients is unable to use complex one (Kerssens et al., 2015). With respect to the perspective of caregivers, some solutions are useful to study and monitor the behavior of the patient in order to avoid risky situations. To this extent Magnusson et al. (2013) adopts a GPS alarm to monitor the patient. In other studies, sensors are implanted in wearable device in order to detect the fall of the person and immediately notifies medical authorities (e.g. smart watches described within the technology domain of the STOF framework §4.1.2). Furthermore, through video cameras, it is possible to study the se-

quences of actions that lead to falls, therefore, it entails a higher effectiveness in fall prevention (Robert et al., 2013; Robinovitch et al., 2013). Following Mulvenna (2010), it is possible to reduce the risk related to falls during night through a pressure sensor embedded in the bed that turns on the lights when the patient has vacated the bed.

- **Provide group therapies and stimulate senses:** multisensory stimulations involving music, colors and scents can positively affect the health of the patient and reduce symptoms of depression (Ógáin & Mountain, 2015).
- **Support patient or caregiver to navigate the care system:** the solution can provide information about the care system and support to operate within it in a personalized way. It can inform patient and/or caregiver about his entitlements and this process of providing information has to be pursued with the right timing (Ógáin & Mountain, 2015). The system supports the caregiver in finding the best healthcare specialist or organization that treat the specific pathology.

According to the specific solution and its related devices, it is necessary an assessment regarding any environmental barrier that could avoid accessibility of the technology for the patient inside his house.

Most of these aspects were also confirmed by the outcomes from the CCWs analyzed through the STOF framework. With a greater level of details, the Service domain (§4.1.1) showed the importance of social inclusion and of the improvements in terms of physical and cognitive health through daily exercises.

From the point of view of the overall system, there are various solutions helpful to the various actors involved in the care process:

- **Health Information Exchange:** a key element should be the sharing of information among all the actors involved in the care process of the patient (Bates, 2015).
- **Integration/Interoperability:** the system should ensure the integration and interoperability for the various entities involved in the care process from the points of view of information shared, applications and information systems adopted, etc. As an example, it could be possible the integration between the health care process and the social care process, especially in the case of a patient with MCI supported by a social worker and not by a relative.
- **Dashboard:** the solution ensures the monitoring of the patient's behavior. Through a set of indicators characterized by a straightforward graphical representation and a warning system, the healthcare specialist and the caregiver could monitor the course of the patient's disease and be alerted about any issues.
- **Provide support to the caregiver:** effective care has a positive impact on the progression of the pathology and on the capacity of the patient to stay at home. Therefore, the support for caregivers, e.g. reduction of stress and improvement in well-being (Hu, Kung, Rummans, Clark, & Lapid, 2015), is relevant because it

affects the quality of life for patient with MCI and dementia (Ógáin & Mountain, 2015). It can be pursued in various ways:

- a. **Improve caregiver's feelings of safety and security:** digital solutions like monitoring and surveillance can enhance the feeling of safety of the caregivers (Baruch, Downs, Baldwin, & Bruce, 2004; Kerssens et al., 2015; Lauriks et al., 2007). This is a key aspect: the technological support not only have to assists patients, but also caregivers, unburdening their activities during the constant taking-care of patients. In this way, also caregivers have benefits from the technologies (Ógáin & Mountain, 2015). Regarding this aspects, periodic follow-up phone calls can be scheduled after the installation of the digital solution, to answer any questions and discover how things are going (Kerssens et al. (2015).
- b. **Single point of contact:** due to the high complexity of the ecosystem of actors involved in the care of patients with MCI and dementia, caregivers could be supported in navigating the system through a single point of contact.
- c. **Ensure information availability and provide peer support:** apps and online platforms can enable the access to information and the collaboration among caregivers through sharing information, suggestions and practical advices.

Support drugs management and organization of caregiver's activities: apps could provide various functionalities i.e. shared calendar and communication tools among caregivers that support the same patient, task allocation and medications management tools (Ógáin & Mountain, 2015).

As seen in §4.1.1, the first elements related to the integration and information exchange are some of the key elements that should be taken into account in developing a BM. As a matter of fact, the participation of the various actors involved in the care process should be the keystone of the service developed.

According to the literature, solutions addressing the needs of patients affected by dementia and MCI can intercept and satisfy “new” needs (“newness”) especially thanks to innovative digital solutions, besides requiring “customization” due to the peculiarities and breadth of the customer segments.

Furthermore, another element that can contribute to create value to the customers is the aforementioned solutions “get the job done”, in the sense that patients are supported in their daily activities.

At last, is important to underline that also the design is an important element, which must be taken into account: the electronic devices must accompany the patients in a

noninvasive and invisible way during their daily activities, not making them feel uncomfortable.

4.2.3 Channels

This building block describes the channels through which a company communicates with its customer segments, with the purpose of deliver a value proposition. In other words, the company's interface with its customers. The channels of a BM can be split into direct channels and indirect channels or into owned channels and partner channels, and they serve several functions including:

- Raising awareness among customers about a company's products and services;
- Helping customers evaluate a company's value proposition;
- Allowing customers to purchase specific products and services;
- Delivering a value proposition to customers;
- Providing post-purchase customer support.

The key questions to be asked when figuring out the channels for a BM are (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010):

- Through which channels do our customer segments want to be reached?
- How are we reaching them now?
- How are our channels integrated?
- Which ones work best?
- Which ones are most cost efficient?
- How are we integrating them with the customer routines?

Through literature analysis, it emerged that the principle ways by which the care service could be delivered to the patient are the following:

- **Caregiver:** the keystone of the relationship between patient and technology. It is also vital for the relationship between patient and healthcare specialist because it is the carrier of information. In the case of family caregiver, he/she is also responsible for the process of choice of the specialist.
- **General practitioner:** he/she is the first actor – after the family caregiver – that takes over the patient. It is the first figure that can diagnose the pathology and support the caregiver.
- **Health care specialists:** specialists are the healthcare provider in charge of the treatment of dementia and MCI patients; to this extent they could suggest the use of an appropriate technology to fulfill their needs (van Meeuwen, van Walt Meijer, & Simonse, 2015).
- **Healthcare structures/facilities:** there are specific healthcare organizations who provide care services to elderly people; such organizations could be funded by the municipality. Once a disease is diagnosed to patients, they are sent to such organizations providing care services (van Meeuwen, van Walt Meijer, & Simonse, 2015). To this regard, healthcare structure and facilities can represent a way through which delivering technological product/services to patients.

Channels regarding the overall system are the following:

- **Internet:** an online platform to share information with healthcare specialists and caregivers, could also be a mean to provide products/services to treat dementia (van Meeuwen, van Walt Meijer, & Simonse, 2015).
- **Pharmacies:** as a physical structure, they can be a channel to retail and advertise digital devices addressing directly to the caregiver.
- **Providers of digital solutions:** the providers of digital solutions themselves could sell the solutions to patients (van Meeuwen, van Walt Meijer, & Simonse, 2015) through their caregivers.

As mentioned above, service delivering can be direct (provider and patient interface without intermediaries) or indirect (provider and patient interface through intermediaries). From this point of view, an element that must be taken into account is the relevance of the role played by caregivers and general practitioners as the interface between the patient and the digital service solution. As stated before, their importance is positively related to the severity of cognitive impairment that involves a reduction of patient's autonomy.

Considering the mean age of the patients, the channel will be mainly indirect, therefore some of the aforementioned examples of channels (i.e. internet and pharmacies) will have the caregiver as the main interlocutor.

Another peculiar aspect concerning digital service solutions and their multifaceted features (i.e. they involve various elements like hardware, software, information, data, etc.) is that the service delivery could require the right mix of channels. As an example regarding a hypothetical wearable device, internet and the healthcare specialist could be channels to inform the caregiver about the potential benefits of the specific solution, the caregiver will convince the patient about it. Then, the wearable device could be delivered directly to the patient without the interface of the healthcare specialist or of the caregiver.

Thus, it can be seen that the BM employs the direct and as well as its partner channels to reach its customers. Nevertheless, it should be kept in mind that finding the right mix of channels to satisfy how the customers want to be reached is crucial in bringing a value proposition to the market.

4.2.4 Customer Relationships

This building block describes how the company relates with its customer segments: different relationships take place – from personal to automated – usually driven by customer acquisition, customer retention and boosting sales.

Customer relations are classified into the following categories, which may coexist in a company's relation with a specific customer segment (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010):

- **Personal assistance:** based on human relation, a communication is provided—during the sales process—between the customer and a customer representative.
- **Dedicated personal assistance:** a customer representative is completely dedicated to a client.
- **Self service:** no direct relationships are maintained with the client, to whom are supplied all the tools directly so that he can serves himself.
- **Automated service:** automated services simulate a personal relationship with a customer through a self-service logic.
- **Communities:** these online communities allow customers to exchange information and advises each others. At the same time, communities also allow companies to better understand their customers.
- **Co-creation:** this involves customers co-creating value with the companies, like inviting people to write review about a product.

The end user usually communicates with the caregiver (or with a social worker) and this relationship is the starting point for every digital solution involving patients with MCI or dementia. Considering the need for constant supervision of dementia and MCI patients, a “personal assistance” it is the kind of relation that should be established. As previously mentioned, the role played by the caregiver is often relevant and this relevance is positively related to the severity of the cognitive impairment. Requiring an interface between patient and healthcare specialist, caregivers or social workers are the key actors that relate with patient segments. Furthermore, they support the patient in the adoption and usage of the digital solution. They should present the digital solution and explain the utility connected with its usage in order to foster its acceptance by the patient. Therefore, caregivers are also the key interface between patient and digital technologies.

From the system standpoint, many companies maintain online most of their relationships with caregivers (Trequattrini, Lombardi, Lardo, Rosa, & Bolici, 2015)—for example through blogs, establishing a “community” and a “Co-creation” relation. Caregivers can share experiences with both the community and the company, but also provide feedback on a particular product/service (van Meeuwen, van Walt Meijer, & Simonse, 2015). In this sense, company can take advantage of these feedbacks. Companies could also achieve crucial data about the patients and the caregiver himself, for example about their needs.

Another element that should be taken into account is the relationship between the service provider and the healthcare organization or healthcare specialist that treats the patient. In the first case, if the relationship is related to a complex healthcare organization, it can be a “dedicated personal assistance”, otherwise, if a dedicated and personalized contact is not vital, it could be a “personal assistance”.

4.2.5 Revenue Streams

This sub-paragraph deals with the cash a company generates from every customer segment: each revenue stream could have different pricing mechanisms, for example fixed list prices, auctioning, market dependent, bargaining, volume dependent or yield management. A BM involves two different types of revenue streams:

- Revenues from one-time customer payments;
- Recurrent revenues deriving from ongoing payments gained from the delivery of the value proposition, or providing post purchase support to the customer.

The different ways in which revenue can be generated are the following ones:

- **Asset sales:** is about selling the ownership rights about a physical product.
- **Usage fee:** the user pays proportionally to the use of the service.
- **Subscription fee:** users pays continuous access to a service.
- **Lending/renting/leasing:** a user has the exclusive rights to use a particular asset for a fixed period, in return for a fee.
- **Licensing:** allowing the customer to use protected intellectual property in exchange for licensing fees.
- **Brokerage fee:** derives from the intermediation services performed on behalf of two or more parties.
- **Advertising:** the revenue stream is generated from fees for advertising a product, brand or service.

Following Stroetmann et al. (2003), who have analyzed the implementation of tele-care services, it emerges that the main revenues streams for a digital solution are the following:

- Service paid by insurance funds;
- Service paid by governments;
- Service paid by the patient or by his relatives/caregiver through out-of-pocket expenses.

In general, three groups of people or organizations pay for the digital solution:

- **Business to Consumer (B2C):** the service is sold directly to the patient or his caregiver. This includes those that directly fund their care and those that exploit personal budget related to local authorities.
- **Business to Public sector (B2P):** the service is sold to public entities i.e. local authorities, National Health Systems and housing associations
- **Business to Business (B2B):** the service is sold to private companies and in some countries most of them are private medical insurance companies.

The first is related to the patient's point of view, while the last two groups represent the point of view of the overall system. Furthermore, there could be the following types of transactions between the provider of digital solutions and the healthcare organization:

- Healthcare organization purchases the entire system (one-time capital investment);
- Healthcare organization pays a license fee for each patient connected to the system.

With respect to the payer of the digital solution, further analysis specific to the context of the pilots will exploit which entity/person is in charge of the prescription for this kind of solutions.

Considering the different National Health Systems, governments can contribute to pay part of the medical expenses of their citizens. Kapadia et al. (2015) analyzing the governmental contribution pointed out that governments could also financially support the implementation phase that requires initial expenses, such as training activities, hardware and software.

These country-specific aspects, outlined in §0.04.1.4, will be further analyzed in the next activities of the Project.

4.2.6 Key Resources

This sub-paragraph illustrates the essential assets necessary to make a BM work. From the company's viewpoint, these resources enable the creation and offer of a value proposition. Furthermore, they allow to create touch points with the market, to sustain connections with customer segments and to obtain revenues. Finally, they are acquired from partners, owned or rented by the company.

The main questions to address by identifying the Key Resources are the following:

- What key resources do our value propositions require?
- What are "our distribution channels?"
- What are our "customer relationships?"
- What are our "revenue streams?"

All the key resources for a BM can be classified into the following categories (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010):

- **Physical assets:** e.g. buildings, vehicles, machines, manufacturing facilities, distribution networks, etc.
- **Intellectual assets:** e.g. brands, patents, copyrights, proprietary knowledge, etc. They are difficult to be created, nevertheless once realized they often provide huge returns.
- **Human resources:** responsible for all the activities required in a company.
- **Financial resources:** e.g. cash, lines of credit, etc.

From the perspective of the patient, the human resources that will be crucial in the establishment of the BM are health professional and caregivers (or the social worker if the patient has not relatives that support him/her) (Robert et al., 2013). As previously described, the caregiver is the keystone of the overall system and his impor-

tance increases with the severity of the disease. Healthcare professionals act as a channel through which the product/service reach the customers.

From the overall system's perspective, the human resource that is vital in the establishment of the BM is the specialist of digital services that will assist in the manufacturing and the design of the assisting technologies (Kapadia, Ariani, Li, & Ray, 2015).

From the standpoint of physical assets required to provide the service, technologies play a key role both for the patient and for the overall system (i.e. hardware and software) (Bharucha et al., 2009; Kerssens et al., 2015; Robert et al., 2013). They are derived from the specific needs of the patient i.e. from the proposition of the BM. However, other aspects are also relevant because they allow the overall service to work properly (i.e. warehouse, distribution network, communication network) and, ultimately, to satisfy the customer.

From the overall system's viewpoint, other key resources are patents, licenses and copyrights that fall in the intellectual – and intangible - category of the key resources building block.

A role described within the sub-paragraph §4.1.3 and relevant for both the patient and the overall system perspectives is played by the Case manager. He coordinates care activities and information management, provides responses to patients and their families because he has the overall view of the status and evolution of the disease. As showed during the CCCWs, this role is country-specific. As an example, in Sweden this role is played by the nurse or in Israel by the General Practitioner.

4.2.7 Key Activities

This sub-paragraph defines the activities a firm must perform to operate effectively and make its BM work. These activities enable the creation and the offering of a value proposition. Furthermore, they allow to create touch points with the market, to sustain connections with customer segments and to obtain revenues.

The key activities for a BM can be figured out if one asks the following questions.

- What key activities do our value propositions require?
- What are our distribution channels?
- What is our customer relationship?
- What are our revenue streams?

Following Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010) the key activities of a BM can be categorized into the following categories.

- **Production activities:** related to the design, realization and delivery of a product/service. From manufacturing standpoint, they are the most relevant.
- **Problem solving:** related to provide new solutions to individual customers' requirements. From the viewpoint of service providers, these activities are the most important.

- **Platform/network:** activities related to platform and network of complementors (Brandenburger & Nalebuff, 1998; Gawer & Cusumano, 2013). As an example, it is possible to include in this category activities of platform promotion and management.

The first relevant activities are related to the creation and sustainment of the relationships among the key actors of the overall system. They can be summarized as the following:

- Create the connection between healthcare specialist and caregiver/social worker;
- Maintenance of the relationship between healthcare specialist and caregiver/social worker.

From the patient standpoint, the key activities related to his involvement:

- Engagement of the patient;
- Maintenance of the relationship with the patient.

The prerequisite for the engagement of the patient is often the establishment of the relationship between caregiver and healthcare specialist because, regardless of the choices on the channel and digital solutions, these two figures play a key role.

Following Ógáin and Mountain (2015), the aforementioned activities but also those described later related to the patient, can be supported through the contributions of governmental actors in terms of:

- National/regional awareness campaigns;
- Financial incentives to healthcare organizations that offer quality of MCI and dementia care;
- Financial incentives to healthcare specialist for the diagnosis of MCI and dementia;
- Financial incentives to healthcare specialists and healthcare organizations for the adoption of digital solutions to treat MCI and dementia.

As evidenced in Kerssens et al. (2015), a meaningful engagement of the patient is a primary goal in order to encourage the use of technologies and to promote a behavioral change: this kind of engagement and the subsequent maintenance of the relationship can be reached through the personalization of the technologies (Companion project §3.2.1). Furthermore, as depicted in §4.1.1 and in §4.1.2, the overall service should be characterized by personalization and adapted to the individual capabilities.

Following Robert et al. (2013), the major key activities in the BM related to the technology adopted are termed as the following:

- Production of the equipment and the sensors;
- Selection of the most appropriate technology/sensor;
- Installation of the technologies in the patients' home;
- Calibration of the sensors.

With respect to the production and selection of the equipment, authors illustrate that these devices should be easy to install or to be worn and should ease maintenance activities. Furthermore, their response time and sensitivity should be the most appropriate according to the requests of clinicians and, finally, their scope should be easily understandable for the user.

Speaking of personalization and calibration of devices, a prerequisite to successfully promote the adoption of a digital solution by the patient is the mapping of the activities performed by the patient. It is often useful e.g. to choose the most appropriate time window in which the digital solution should act or interact with the patient/caregiver, the most appropriate place in which to place reminders. As depicted in § 4.1.2, technology should be as hidden as possible without interaction with the patient (in the case of a higher severity of the disease). In order to personalize the digital solution, scheduling an interview with both the caregivers and the patient can be useful not only to understand the daily activities, but also to identify interests and routines (Kerssens et al., 2015).

Concerning the last two activities, their correct execution avoids negative effects on the quality of sensor processing. As a matter of fact, the latter is not only a consequence of appropriate choices in terms of design and selection of the equipment. Furthermore, these activities require a high level of personalization to the specific characteristics of the patient and the solution should be properly inserted within his daily activities.

As regards DECI, it could be useful to find the right balance between the different types of key activities, giving due importance without forgetting any one: the production activities play a key role in the development and delivery of the digital devices that, however, was driven by the ability to provide new solutions to the customer segments. In fact, to ensure that the service work properly, is important to manage, and promote, the platforms developed.

Finally, considering the overall system approach, activities of risk assessment should be performed in order to consider the whole safety of the services/solutions provided to the end-users. Risk assessment will prevent from injuries that could occur to users but also protect other stakeholders (such as clinical and/or technological partner) from legal consequences in case of problems in data transmission, database handling, alarm responsiveness, etc.

4.2.8 Key Partnerships

This sub-paragraph illustrates the partnerships, and the network of suppliers, useful to improve the BM, in order to obtain resources and to lower risks. The partnerships can be grouped in the following categories:

- Strategic alliances between non-competitors;

- Strategic alliances between competitors;
- Joint ventures seeking for new business;
- Buyer-supplier relationships, to guarantee high reliability related to supplies.

Following Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010) the reasons to start a partnership can be multiple, and the main one are the following:

- **Optimization and economy of scale (buyer-seller relationship):** it is related to efficiency and to the potential optimal exploitation of resources, reached through outsourcing or sharing infrastructures.
- **Reduction of risk and uncertainty:** it is related to the lowering of risks, due to the uncertainties that characterize competitive environments. The partnership can involve also competitors, which will collaborate within an area while they will continue to compete in other areas.
- **Acquisition of particular resources and activities:** it is related to the possibility to extend the knowledge, the resources and activities on which the company can rely on to deliver the service.

From the point of view of the patient, voluntary associations can be key partners. Following Ógáin and Mountain (2015), unpaid informal care and volunteering activities could be a great help in key activities, as they help in reducing the overall cost of the operations. Limited to the activities in which this is possible, volunteers could be recruited and trained to help in assisting patients, maybe thanks to the technological support, instead of actual professionals doing the job.

Focusing on the overall system, literature suggest that some key partnership for the BM could be:

- Government;
- Research center/university;
- Local regional community (Kapadia et al., 2015);
- Private organization (König et al., 2015);
- Network provider between the provider of digital solutions and healthcare organization.

With respect to the governance of the various National Health Systems, it emerged that the government could also have a role on caregiving centers, therefore it is a key partner to reach the customers. Moreover, since the government provides both the revenue and the necessary connections with the healthcare industry, the government is clearly a key partner in the BM, also because generally pays the expenses of the patients (Kapadia et al. 2015). As described in §4.2.7, the role of governments and local authorities is extremely relevant because they can conduct awareness campaigns, furthermore, they provide incentives related to the quality of MCI and dementia care and to diagnosis of these pathologies. Obviously, this role has to be contextualized within the various National Health System.

As depicted in §4.1.3, also non-governmental organizations and relevant associations can play a key role in the care process for MCI patients.

With respect to the acquisition of particular resources and activities, another key partnership is the one with the research centers and the universities, because they have a key part to play in the research and development of technologies. Besides, involving elderly people during the design process is absolutely critical for developing technologies that meet the needs of the final users (Kapadia et al., 2015). Once the technologies are developed, there is always a need for further research on new prototypes, for constant innovation.

From the discussion between partners of the project, it emerged that other significant partners are the local communities, which are the nearest source of contact with the patient. The local communities can help in assisting people with dementia and MCI: there are many private organizations that are already offering healthcare benefits to the people with dementia and MCI (K. A. Stroetmann et al., 2003).

Moreover, the digital services must be delivered to both the patients in their home and to the medical service provider, not only hospitals, but also local and regional communities (K. A. Stroetmann et al., 2003).

Other actors to be involved are representatives from the industry (i.e. neurologists, psychiatrists, psychologists, engineers) and patient associations. It would be extremely useful to organize workshops with these stakeholders (König et al., 2015). Moreover, it was learnt that looking from the partners' perspective there is another key partnership that can be signed: the one with other organizations, like the one taking care of the old and frail people, or the one which takes care of the people with dementia and MCI.

4.2.9 Cost Structure

This sub-paragraph illustrates the relevant costs that characterizes a feasible BM. The main questions related to the cost structure are the following (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010, p. 41):

- What are the most important cost inherent in our BM?
- Which key resources are the most expensive?
- Which key activities are the most expensive?

The cost structure of an organization can be classified between two extremes:

- **Cost driven:** the focus is on cost's reduction, or wherever is possible on their minimization;
- **Value driven:** in this case, the focus is on the creation of value and not on the underlying costs.

Moreover, the cost structure can have the following features:

- **Fixed cost:** they are invariable despite the volume of the services delivered.

- **Variable cost:** they are proportionally variable with the volume of services delivered.
- **Economies of scale:** a business has cost advantages as volumes increase.
- **Economies of scope:** a business has cost advantages as variety increases.

Literature suggests that the main costs for a digital solution are the following (Kapadia et al. 2015):

- Training costs;
- Personnel costs
- Installation and maintenance costs;
- Purchasing and manufacturing costs;
- Customer service costs.

Several scholars found that the training cost of caregivers would be one of the key spending activity. Talking about new technologies, a significant amount of money should be spent in making the caregivers understand the working of the equipment and its usefulness (Kapadia et al. 2015). Therefore, training positively affects the effectiveness of the usage of the specific solution.

Accordingly to Kapadia et al. (2015) one of the most relevant costs regards the installation cost of the equipment in the patients' home. Installation of the equipment takes labor and a significant part of the cost has to be paid to labors. Since the equipment have to be made from scratch, there would be purchasing and manufacturing cost of the materials required.

After the customers has been provided with the appropriate technologies, there is need for timely maintenance of the devices, to check if they are fully functional or not. Additionally, another maintenance cost could be the customer service cost to help the elderly in using the devices.

In DECI solution, it is reasonable to expect that there will be a mix of these elements: some fixed cost are unavoidable, even if the variable ones will be preponderant. In this sense, rather than an economy of scope – the scope of operations is limited – DECI should be based on an economy of scale, trying to expand its output.

Furthermore, other costs that emerged through the CCWs and highlighted in §0.04.1.4 are the following:

- Data storage and data management costs;
- Purchasing and maintenance of the notification network for the acquisition of alerts costs;
- Information provisioning at patient's and family members' home costs.

5 Conclusions

This chapter synthesizes the main findings of the previously described BM analysis (Chapter 4), grouping the findings of the literature analysis and the evidences related to the STOF framework, and providing a coherent insight with both CCWs and literature evidences. In Figure 5-1 is highlighted the *fil rouge* among the various blocks of the BM arisen from the literature analysis.

The starting point is obviously related to the customer segments that are characterized by 4 key actors (3 related to patients and 1 to the caregiver). Any decision to focus on one or some groups of customers will affect the choices related to the “intermediate” customers i.e. healthcare specialist and healthcare organization. From the system’s perspective, the latter are 2 actors with different needs in terms of coordination, integration, efficiency and effectiveness.

Independently of the choice, the involvement of the patient and of the caregiver is compulsory within the design phase, in order to effectively define how to engage them. The twofold role of the caregiver comprises a component related to the support in technology usage and another one in which the caregiver acts as the connection with the healthcare system. Thus, caregiver is both a recipient of the value proposition and a channel through which it is delivered.

<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Voluntary associations Governments Researchers centers/Universities Local regional community Private organizations Network coordinator between IT providers and healthcare organizations 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creation and sustainment of relationships Activities related to technology Risk assessment Governmental activities <p>Key Resources</p> <p>Human</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specialist of digital technologies Caregiver/Social worker Healthcare professionals <p>Intellectual</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patents, licenses and copyrights <p>Physical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Warehouse Distribution network Communication network Hardware and software 	<p>Value Proposition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess linguistic capabilities Early detection of dementia Provide rich audio-visual programs Simulate presence and support to dial relatives Routines –reminders (activities of daily living) Foster reminiscence Support for pleasure activities Enhance the feelings of safety Study he circumstances of falls and rest-activity patterns Provide group therapies and stimulate senses Support to navigate the care system Health Information Exchange Integration/Interoperability Dashboard Provide support to the caregiver 	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal assistance (Caregiver-Patient) Personal assistance (Service provider-Healthcare organization/specialist) Co-creation: feedback, ideas, suggestions <p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Caregiver General practitioner Health care specialists Healthcare structures/facilities Internet Pharmacies Providers of digital solutions 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patients with dementia Patients with Amnestic MCI (a-MCI) Patients with Non Amnestic MCI (na-MCI) <p>Or</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Caregiver Healthcare specialists/providers Healthcare structures/facilities
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training costs of caregivers Personnel costs Installation costs Maintenance costs Purchasing costs (software and hardware) 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business to Consumer (B2C): service sold directly to the patient/caregiver Business to Public sector (B2P): local authorities, National Health Systems Business to Business (B2B): insurances Healthcare organization purchases the entire system (one-time capital investment) Healthcare organization pays a license fee for each patient 		

Figure 5-1 Summary of the main evidences from literature analysis

As described before there is a multitude of complementary channels that are mixed, and most of them are indirect and involve not only the caregivers as a key figure, but also the GPs.

The value propositions are various and most of them seems to be characterized by being complementary to each other, both from the patient perspective and the system perspective. This aspect deserves further analysis in order to discover all the synergies among these value propositions that could exploit the potential related to them. As highlights the *service domain* of the STOF framework, through services constructed around physical and cognitive health enhancement, social inclusion, self-monitoring and preventive actions informed by data, is possible to improve the wellness of the MCI-affected individuals. However, providing an effective monitoring system or a reminder without establishing a proper solution of data integration among actors that allows also the collaboration of the GP (e.g. providing him/her information about rest patterns or adherence to reminders) will result as a poor solution. Furthermore, this aspect should be contextualized within the various National Health Systems – with all their peculiarities – in which the BM will be designed and developed.

Finally, the choice on the specific needs to be addressed narrows the focus on only those technologies coherent with these needs and involves the exclusion of other incoherent solutions. According to the project, this exercise will be accomplished through WP3 (Design of the Digital Environment for Cognitive Inclusion)

The activities required to design, develop and sustain the BM are various and from the patient's perspective are related to the relationship with him/her or to the technology adopted. Nevertheless, in both cases a high level of personalization is required, for instance when technology should be adapted specifically to the map of patient's activities. This need for customization, also discussed during the CCWs, results in an increase of costs but also allows to better address the patient's needs therefore the challenge is in providing both efficiency and effectiveness through the same digital solution (O'Reilly & Tushman, 2013). Generally, with regard to the STOF *technology domain*, during the CCWs were discussed two types of technology scenarios which could be implemented: an "information system scenario", which enable information exchange between stakeholders, and a "monitoring system scenario", which enable alerts and notifications based on patient data.

According to the customer segments addressed with specific value propositions, the business relationships that generates revenue streams can involve three market segments: the end-user (B2C), another business company (B2B) or public administration (B2P). The kind of relationships strongly depends on the specific characteristic of National Health System. As previously mentioned, further analysis context-based will be held within WP3 and its tasks. At the CCWs, inquiring the STOF finance domain, were already identified the key areas of cost, that for example can concern

costs for personnel, device implementation and usage, data storage and management, maintenance, etc.

Finally, the effective adoption and use of every digital solution often depends on the governmental actions in terms of incentives, awareness campaigns or norms. Therefore, governments but also local communities and voluntary associations should be considered as key partners and involved during the design of the BM. In order to avoid an unmanageable increase in complexity, their aims and focus should be clearly defined and bounded.

As it is clearly described before, the context heavily influences all the blocks of the BMC, therefore also the interplay among key resources – useful to design, develop and sustain the BM – depends on contextual factors. Also at the CCWs, discussing about the STOF *organization domain*, emerged that each country must search for its proper organisational design to manage the implementation and management of the developed business model. Anyway, all the four partner countries recognize the relevance of the “Case Manager” role.

Figure 5-2 summarizes the main evidence produced within the present task and contained in this deliverable. This output will be further explored and adapted to the specific context in which DECI project operates in order to consider specific constraints and to appraise local excellences. Later analysis, conducted within WP3, will pursue the aim to narrow the different opportunities and options widely presented in this deliverable. In particular, a context-specific BM is the output of Task 3.1.

<p>Key Partners </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very high number of customer segments • 4 key actors: choice over whom focusing • 2 actors with different needs from a system perspective (coordination, intergration and efficiency) 				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three payment systems: B2C, B2P, B2B — depending on the national healthcare systems (more info are needed on the various contexts) • Licence fee versus one-time capital investment (not necessarily alternatives) 				

Figure 5-2 Synthesis of BM

6 Main References Considered

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